

IGNATIAN

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR
MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

www.icceph.com

ISSN 2984-9942

**THE FEASIBILITY OF ESTABLISHING A MANUFACTURING COMPANY IN THE
PHILIPPINES THAT PRODUCES CORN/SOY MEAL TO REDUCE MALNUTRITION
AMONG CHILDREN IN THE PHILIPPINES**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10781421>

ABSTRACT

This feasibility study was done to determine the feasibility of establishing a manufacturing company that produces Corn/Soymeal to reduce malnutrition among children in the Philippines. In this feasibility study, both quantitative and qualitative methodology was used to carry out the feasibility studies. In the quantitative methodology, statistical data was gathered from the Department of Education (DepED), the World Food Programme, and other important agencies, both public and private, as well as international organizations whereas for the qualitative methodology, interviews were conducted at the DepEd to get more information about the market, industry. The research paradigm followed an interpretive school of thought. The variables used in this research were independent and dependent variables. Some of the dependent variables were the data obtained from interviews conducted at DepEd. The independent variables were the DepEd employees and the World Food Programme because the findings of the feasibility studies depended on the data they provided. It was discovered that there is a considerable market opportunity for Corn/Soy meal in Metro Manila and that the utilization of recent and highly advanced types of machinery equipment will give the business a huge potential for success and increased productivity.

Keywords: *Malnutrition, quantitative methodology, qualitative methodology, variables, Independent variables, Dependent variables*

INTRODUCTION

Malnutrition is very present in underdeveloped countries in the world. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines good nutrition as the adequate, well-balanced intake of food in relation to the body's dietary needs. Malnutrition is an encompassing term for the various forms of poor nutrition, whether it is excess consumption of nutrients (overnutrition) usually afflicting the obese, or inadequate consumption of nutrients (undernutrition) common with those suffering from extreme and prolonged hunger. The National Capital Region (NCR) of the Philippines has many depressed areas. Some of these areas include Tondo, San Andres of the City of Manila, Batasan Hills, Bagong Silangan, Payatas of Quezon city, West Rembo of Makati City, and Barangay Sta. Lucia of Pasig City, Libertad of Pasay City, and Kabihasanan area of Paranaque City.

When assessed along with the Child Growth Standards set by WHO, child undernutrition has three indicators: underweight (low weight-for-age, including low birth weight), wasting (low weight-for-height), and stunting (low height-for-age). An exhaustive 54-country study of maternal and child undernutrition published in 2010 in *The Lancet*, one of the world's oldest and prestigious weekly peer-reviewed general medical journals, "found that height-for-age at two years was the best predictor of human capital and that undernutrition is associated with lower human capital." It also stressed that "it is during the child's first 1000 days when the most pronounced growth reduction is observed compared to other stages in a child's development." There's also a World Bank study that found out that "a one-percent loss in adult height as a result of childhood stunting is linked with a 1.4-percent loss in economic productivity, resulting in 20 percent less earnings as adult." It added that stunting "is associated with up to 3 percent GDP losses annually."

The non-government organization, Save the Children Philippines, also made an in-depth study in 2016 which revealed that "education and productivity losses as a result of child undernutrition amounted to a total of 1,328 billion in 2013." The amount was equivalent to 2.84 % of the Philippines' GDP that year. The study pointed out that of the 330,418 students who repeated a grade level in 2013, about 15% or 48,597 students "had repeated a grade level as a result of under-five stunting. An additional 11.23 billion was required to cover the costs of grade-level repetitions for these stunted children." It said that stunting costs the Philippines some 1,326.5 billion in lost productivity. To address undernutrition among public school students, the Department of Education in 2016 asked schools to establish the *Gulayan sa Paaralan Program (GPP)* "as a source of ingredients for the School-Based Feeding Program and encourage families of beneficiaries to have their own home garden for the continuous nutritional improvement at home."

The F. Serrano Sr. Elementary School in Paranaque City is among the best to implement GPP. "The school boasts some fruit-bearing trees, urban vertical gardening, containerized gardening, aquaponics, circulating and non-circulating hydroponics, and fishponds. The non-circulating hydroponics will be seen on every floor of the school building. The school harvests organic vegetables such as pechay, mustard, and eggplants which are used as ingredients for the school's feeding program," DepEd said.

The successful implementation of GPP in the most impoverished areas of the country will go a long way in battling undernutrition (Att.Joey.D.Lina, Joey. 2018).

The invaluable help of the private sector and more NGOs will certainly boost efforts to rid the menace plaguing Filipino children. And foremost among these efforts ought to be poverty reduction.” In the year 2013 my sister who was a Registered State Nurse working in a Gynecology and Obstetrics hospital in Yaoundé, Cameroon, saw cases of malnutrition in the pediatric ward of the hospital. After some months of experimenting and research, she and another partner came up with a perfect blend of soy/corn meal named SIM & NAMY –Bouillie de Royaume au Soja which was validated as nutritious by a government-owned laboratory in Cameroon known as the Cameroun Laboratoire d’analyse Physiochimiques (The Cameroon Laboratory for Physiochemical Analysis). Associating the researcher’s knowledge of the soy/corn meal business back in Cameroon with the feasibility studies in Metro Manila, the researcher came up with a feasibility study on how to establish a soy/corn meal-producing factory in Metro Manila in 2019. The products of the soy/corn meal are intended to be sold to the Department of Education, Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), non-government institutions, charitable organizations, and local municipalities, all of which have feeding programs to help address malnutrition of public school students. To objective is to determine the feasibility of establishing a manufacturing company in the Philippines that produces Corn/Soy meals to reduce malnutrition among children in the Philippines.

The general objective of this feasibility study is to determine the feasibility of establishing a manufacturing company in the Philippines that produces Corn/Soy meals to reduce malnutrition among children in the Philippines. The specific objective is to determine the specific resources that will be needed to establish a company that makes Corn/Soy meals. When taking into consideration the Marketing, Management, Technical, and Financial aspects. The feasibility study also has short-term and long-term objectives. In terms of short-term objectives, the project intends to improve the health of its consumers, especially malnourished children, by providing them with essential nutrients.

Another short-range objective is to make the soy/corn meal very affordable to the Department of Education, Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), Non-government institutions and charitable organizations, and local municipalities by reducing the cost of production of the soy/corn meal. As for the long-term objective the project intends to make the soy/corn product compete internationally. The project intends to introduce the soy/corn meal in the ASEAN market and in other areas of the world that don’t have the same or similar products. This will allow the company to be more profitable. In addition, the project aims to establish different branches in Asia, Africa, and Europe. Another long-term objective is to constantly provide donors to international organizations like UNICEF and the World Health Organization (WHO) so that they can assist less developed countries.

Soybean helps malnourished children to gain weight. A study was conducted to determine the effect of two soybean-based products on malnourished children under five years in the Ruhango district in Rwanda (Africa). From the study only soybean flour, soybean milk,

and tofu were well-known soybean products in the Ruhango District. Soybean flour was mixed with vegetables and other foods. The intervention with soybean milk and soybean soup had improved the nutritional status of malnourished children. The means weight gain of children using soybean milk and soybean soup was high: 0.9 kg for soybean milk treatment and 0.9 kg for soybean soup (Niyibituronsa M1, Kyallo F, Mugo C and S Gaidashova , 2014).

Establishing good eating habits early in life is important. Childhood dietary intake may impact adult chronic disease risk and influence eating habits in adulthood. Soy foods provide important options for improving the diets of young people and research shows that these foods are acceptable to children. Therefore, soy foods can be viewed as healthy additions to the diets of children and adolescents. Other than relatively rare soy protein allergy, there is no clinical evidence that soy foods exert any adverse effects. On the contrary, there is evidence suggesting that exposure to soy during childhood and/or adolescence reduces breast cancer risk later in life (Messina, Mark, PhD). More recently, researchers from the National Cancer Institute reported that, in comparison to low-soy consumers, women who were classified as high-soy consumers at ages 5-11, 12-19, and 20+ years, were 58, 21 and 29 percent less likely to develop breast cancer, respectively (Korde LA, Wu AH, Fears T, et al., 2006).

Also, a just-published U.S. study found that higher soy food intake during adolescence was associated with a 28 percent reduction in adult breast cancer risk, whereas consuming higher amounts of soy during adulthood was only very modestly protective (Wu AH, Yu MC, Tseng CC, Stanczyk FZ, Pike MC, 2009). Soy foods are generally well-accepted by children according to studies (Ashraf HR, Schoeppel C, Nelson JA, 1990). For example, among preschool children aged three to six years who attended a Head Start program, children consumed soy-enhanced lunches as readily as those made with more traditional ingredients, as evidenced by the amounts eaten (Endres J, Barter S, Theodora P, Welch P, 2003).

Short-term studies show that soy foods support the normal growth and development of children, and improve growth when substituted for legumes in the diets of malnourished pre-schoolers (Kay T, Ifeacho CL, Onowu G, et al, 1975). As in adults, 61 clinical research in children shows that soy protein directly lowers serum cholesterol levels and improves levels of other lipids. (Laurin D, Jacques H, Moorjani S, et al, 1991). In the most recent study, when soy protein (average intake 0.5 g/kg body weight) was incorporated into the diets of children and adolescents (mean age, 8.8 years; range 4-18 years) with familial and polygenic hypercholesterolemia, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol decreased by 6.4 percent beyond the 11 percent decrease that occurred in response to the adoption of a standard low-saturated fat diet during the three-month run-in period (Weghuber D, Widhalm K, 2008). More so one recent study reported that more than 80 percent of infants outgrew their soy allergy by two years of age (Aaronov D, Tasher D, Levine A, Somekh E, Serour F, Dalal ,2008).

Research Questions

1. Can we establish a manufacturing company in the Philippines that produces Corn/Soy meals to reduce malnutrition among children in the Philippines?
 2. Can a combination of Corn and Soybean be used to treat malnutrition?
 3. Is there a market in the Philippines for a manufacturing company that produces Corn/Soy meals to reduce malnutrition among children in the Philippines?
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METHODOLOGY

The secondary data used in this study was gathered from the Department of Education (DepEd), the World Food Programme, and other important agencies, both public and private, as well as international organizations. Interviews were conducted at the DepEd to get more information about the market and the industry. In this feasibility study, both quantitative and qualitative methodology was used to carry out the feasibility studies. In the quantitative methodology, statistical data was gathered from the Department of Education (DepEd), the World Food Programme, and other important agencies, both public and private, as well as international organizations whereas for the qualitative methodology, interviews were conducted at the DepEd to get more information about the market and the industry. The variables used in this research were independent and dependent variables. Some of the dependent variables were the data obtained from interviews conducted at DepEd meanwhile the independent variables were the DepEd employees and the World Food Programme. In this feasibility study, SWOT analysis, demand analysis, ratio analysis, and sensitivity analysis were used.

RESULTS

The gross margin ratio is 83% which implies the company will retain 0.83 pesos for each peso of revenue generated. In addition, the net profit margin ratio is 18% which implies that for every peso generated by the company in sales, the company will keep 0.18 pesos as profit. As for the return on the investment, the company will make an ROI of 14%. The break-even analysis gives us 74%. Finally, a sensitivity analysis was done in this feasibility study and it took into account the fluctuation in the cost of raw materials (soy and corn). The sensitivity analysis demonstrated that the gross profits made by the company are directly influenced by the prices of the raw materials as well as by the cost of production. It is noticed that as the prices of all raw materials increase the cost of production also increases thereby leading to a constant fall in gross profits.

DISCUSSION

Malnutrition is a problem in the Philippines so this feasibility study was done to determine the feasibility of establishing a manufacturing company in the Philippines that produces Corn/Soymeal to reduce malnutrition among children in the Philippines. While doing this feasibility study certain key findings were noted. It was discovered that there is a considerable market opportunity for Corn/Soy meal in Metro Manila and that the utilization of recent and highly advanced machinery and equipment gives the business a huge potential for success and increased productivity. Also, a SWOT analysis, demand analysis, ratio analysis, break-even analysis, and sensitivity analysis will be very important for the realization of establishing a manufacturing company in the Philippines that produces Corn/Soymeal to reduce malnutrition among children in the Philippines. In the SWOT analysis, we have strengths like providing the customers with healthy and organic products, which will improve the overall health of children and help malnourished children to gain good weight. The weaknesses include limited capital investment and also the production capacity in the first years of operations cannot satisfy the large demand of the government and charitable organizations. The opportunities on the other hand will include the availability of the raw materials used in making the soy/corn meal in the Philippines, the availability of funds, the constant initiatives and concerns expressed by the Department of Education, Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) to eradicate undernourishment cases in the Philippines and the presence of charitable organizations who also aim at eradicating malnutrition in the Philippines. Finally, the threats will include bad climatic conditions in the Philippines such as strong typhoons which may reduce the amount of corn or maize harvested thus limiting the production of soy/corn meal in return, and the occurrence of high inflation rates in the Philippines. The feasibility study had some limitations. It did not interview all the employees at the DepEd or make sure that those who were interviewed had sufficient knowledge of malnutrition among children in the Philippines and sufficient knowledge of the market and industry. For the ratio analysis, we can observe certain limitations. For example, the net profit margin does not provide insight as to whether management is managing its production cost. In addition, the return on investment in the ratio analysis does not take into account the time value of money and the break-even analysis does not take into account competitors and it does not also take into account the fluctuation of the prices of raw materials in the future.

Conclusions

The feasibility study revealed that the establishment of a manufacturing company in the Philippines that produces Corn/Soy meals to reduce malnutrition among children in the Philippines is very possible. Due to its similar protein content to that of cow's milk, soybean milk can be used to treat malnutrition. When corn and soya beans are combined, malnourished kids can acquire weight and maintain their health extremely quickly. This is one of the main blended foods that the World Food Programme (WFP) distributes to fight malnutrition. The business has a large potential for growth in the Philippines and so

entrepreneurs should invest in this specific market since there are significant profits to be obtained from this business.

Recommendations

The author believes that there is a huge market for any investor who engages in this sector of activity as the economy of the Philippines continues to grow. It is recommended that more entrepreneurs should invest in this specific market since there are significant profits to be obtained from this business

Compliance with ethical standards

The respondent's well-being in this study was safeguarded. Their names were not divulged and they remained anonymous. There was no plagiarism or bias in the interpretation of the findings and the results of the findings were used solely for research purposes.

Acknowledgments

First, I would like to thank God Almighty for helping me to realize this feasibility study. The Journey was a tough one but God Almighty helped me to weather the storm.

I would like to show my gratitude to my elder brother Mr. Metuge Messangwe Atohen Samore and his Wife, Mrs. Ariane Stérin Metuge Messangwe, as well as their son, Metuge Messangwe Massango Alexandre, for allowing me to travel to the Philippines to do a master's degree in Business Administration. I pray that God Almighty will bless them abundantly for their immense support.

I wish to present my special thanks to my elder sister, Mrs. Metuge Ankhesnamon Ya-Nyonge, and Mr. Simeon Noah, for their prayers and also for helping me with valuable data for the feasibility study, my parents Dr. Metuge Enongene and Mrs. Metuge Georgina Pet (Doctor), my elder sisters, Ms. Metuge Nefertiti Nene Dione and Mrs. Metuge Fahtia Pet Mesohde Epse. Ognokem for their timely support, blessings, and prayers as well as my nieces Akinkugbe Nene Bidemi Pet, Ognokem Olas Manuella Anaëlle, and nephew Ognokem Sone Jeremy Nathan for their prayers.

I would like to show my warm thanks to my beautiful wife, Attorney Edan Cañete-Metuge Kogeh for her prayers and immense moral, physical, and financial support throughout the conduct of this feasibility study as well as my son Metuge Kogeh Agila Cañete. My wife played a huge role in helping me realize this feasibility study.

I would also like to thank my thesis adviser, Mr. Philip M. Flores of the Graduate School of Business at Arellano University. He was always available whenever I had a question about my research. He consistently allowed this paper to be my work but steered me in the right direction whenever he thought I needed it. Lastly, I would like to thank Professor Emiliano T. Hudtohan of Jose Rizal University for his help in writing this research paper.

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